

May 1, 2025

JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE
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International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 10.05.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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STAPHYLOCOCCUS LACTIS VA LACTOCOCCUS LACTIS NING OZIQ- OVQAT SANOATIDAGI AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi *Staphylococcus lactis* va *Lactococcus lactis* bakteriyasining ekologik, biotexnologik, farmatsevtika, oziq-ovqat sohasidagi ahamiyati yoritilgan. *S. lactis* bakteriyasi oziq-ovqat sanoatida muhim rol o'ynaydi. U sut mahsulotlarini fermentatsiya qilishda ishtirok etib, mahsulotlarning ta'mi, tuzilishi va saqlanish muddatini yaxshilaydi. Shu bilan birga, *S. lactis* oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarida patogen mikroorganizmlarning o'sishini to'xtatib, ularning xavfsizligini ta'minlaydi. U sut mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarishda ishlatilishi, ekologik muhitni himoya qilishi, biotexnologik jarayonlarda fermentlar ishlab chiqarishi va probiotik sifatida inson salomatligiga foydali ta'sir ko'rsatishi bilan qadrlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Staphylococcus lactis*, pishloq tayyorlash, sut kislotasi, antibiotiklar, protein, shtamm, *gramm-musbat*, *Lactococcus lactis*

Kirish: *Lactococcus lactis* patogen bo'lmagan AT (antimikrob ta'sir) ga boy *gramm-musbat* bakteriya bo'lib, o'simliklardan ajratilgan va faqat kavsh qaytaruvchi hayvonlar tomonidan iste'mol qilinganidan keyin faol bo'lib, oshqozon-ichak traktida ko'payadi. [1]. *Streptococcus* jinsi bilan chambarchas bog'liq va eng ko'p ishlatiladi. Shuningdek, u eng yaxshi tavsiflangan sut kislotasi bakteriyasidir. *Lactococcus lactis* asrlar davomida oziq-ovqat, ayniqsa pishloq, yogurt, tuzlangan karam va shunga o'xshashlarni fermentatsiyalashda ishlatilgan. Fenotipik jihatdan u gram-musbat, sharsimon, gomolaktatli, sporulasiz va fakultativ anaerob ichak bakteriyalari sifatida tasniflanadi. [2, 5]

Lactococcus lactis fermentatsiya sanoatida muhim rol o'ynaydi, bu yerda u bir qator fermentlangan mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishda qo'llaniladi. Sanoat oziq-ovqat fermentatsiyasidagi ahamiyati tufayli *L. lactis* bir asrdan ko'proq vaqt davomida fundamental tadqiqotlar mavzusi bo'ldi. Dastlab *Bacterium lactis* deb ta'riflangan, u birinchi navbatda *Streptococcus lactis* va keyinchalik *Lactococcus lactis* sifatida qayta tasniflangan. [3, 4]

Lactococcus lactis pishloq pishishida muhim bo'lgan sut kislotasi bakteriyasidir. Cheddar va Saint-Paulin pishloqlarida mavjud. *L. lactis* 30 ° C dan -20 ° C gacha saqlangan. *L. lactis* ning hujayra yuzasi tarkibi oqsilga nisbatan polisaxaridning katta miqdorda ko'pligini ko'rsatadi. Bu *L. lactis* subsp ning boshqa shtammining erkin bog'langan hujayra sirt materiali bilan olingan natijalarga mos

keladi. Bundan tashqari, *L. lactising* boshqa shtammlari yuzasida mavjud bo'lgan fag retseptorlari asosan uglevod qismlarida joylashganligi aniqlanganligi bilan ham mos keladi. [4]

Lactococcus lactis dori tayyorlashda katta ahamiyatga ega. *L. lactis*da protein ishlab chiqarish uchun afzal qilingan SP asosiy ajralib chiqadigan laktokokkal oqsil Usp45 dan olingan. *L. lactis* turli proteazlarga sezgir oqsillarni, jumladan emlash uchun potentsial antijenlarni ishlab chiqarishda ham ishlatilishi mumkin. Pishloq pishishi davrida kazeinning parchalanishida proteolizning muhim roliga qaramasdan, *L. lactis* oqsil ishlab chiqarishga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan uchta asosiy proteazdan ko'p bo'lmagan holda ishlab chiqaradi. Pishloq ishlab chiqarish uchun zarur bo'lgan asosiy ajratilgan proteaz PrtP hisoblanadi, ammo bu plazmid bilan kodlangan ferment sutdan boshqa muhitda *L. lactis* o'sishi uchun zarurdir. [5]

Xulosa

Lactococcus lactis – *Staphylococcus lactis* mikroorganizmi oziq-ovqat, biotexnologiya va farmatsevtika sohalarida muhim ahamiyatga ega. U sut mahsulotlarini fermentatsiya qilishda qo'llanilib, mahsulotlarning ta'mi, tuzilishi va saqlash muddatini yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Biotexnologiyada esa ushbu bakteriya fermentlar ishlab chiqarishda va probiotik sifatida qo'llaniladi. Farmatsevtikada *S. lactis* tabiiy antibiotik va bioaktiv moddalar ishlab chiqarish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lib, dori-darmon tayyorlashda qo'llanilishi mumkin. Shuningdek, uning immunitetni mustahkamlash va ichak mikroflorasini yaxshilash xususiyatlari probiotik preparatlar yaratishda ahamiyatlidir.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, *Staphylococcus lactis* ning morfologik tuzilishi va kimyoviy tarkibi uning sanoat tarmoqlarida samarali qo'llanilishiga asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Kelajakda ushbu bakteriyaning qo'llanilish doirasini kengaytirish va yangi farmatsevtik preparatlar ishlab chiqarishda foydalanish istiqbollari mavjud.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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